

If it quacks like a noun, is it a noun?

A reanalysis of English past participles as nouns

Is the past participle used with the verb *have* actually a noun? Hear me out.

#1 There's the same expansion

We expand the verb *have* by adding a noun:

I have a cat.

verb *have* + noun *a cat*

Therefore, could the past participle also be a noun?

I have eaten.

verb *have* + noun *eaten*

#2 There's the same implied prior action

If someone *has* something, they must have acquired that thing at some point before a referenced point in time:

She has a car. (At some point before now, she acquired a car.)

By 2020, Leyla had a nice house. (At some point before 2020, Leyla acquired a house.)

By that point, he will have a dog. (At some point before that future point, he will acquire a dog.)

If someone *has done* something, they must have performed that action at some point before a referenced point in time:

She has eaten it. (At some point before now, she ate it.)

By 2020, Leyla had gotten married. (At some point before 2020, Leyla had gotten married.)

By that point, he will have died. (At some point before that future point, he will die.)

#3 There's the same pattern with gerunds

We create nouns (gerunds) from verbs by adding a suffix (...ing) and then use those same nouns as adjectives (present participles) in constructions that people analyse as somehow "verbal":

verb play + ...ing > noun playing > adjective playing

Playing chess is kinda fun.

noun playing

I am playing chess.

adjective playing

Do we also create nouns (insert a cool new name here) from verbs by adding a suffix (...ed) and then use those same nouns as adjectives (past participles) in constructions that people analyse as somehow “verbal”?

verb play + ...ed > noun played > adjective played

I have played chess.

noun played

The game was played.

adjective played

Similarly, we don't usually pluralise either created noun:

* I hate playings chess.

* I have playeds chess.

We don't usually use determiners with either created noun:

* I hate the playing chess.

* I have the played chess.

We expand both nouns in the same way as the verbs they are created from:

Cleaning is boring.

Cleaning your room is boring.

noun cleaning + noun your room

I have cleaned.

I have cleaned your room.

noun cleaned + noun your room

? I hate feeling.

I hate feeling inferior.

noun feeling + adjective inferior

? I have felt.

I have felt inferior.

noun felt + adjective inferior

Are you convinced?